

Effect of Macroions on the Apparent pK and Visible Spectra of pH -Indicators. I. Congo Red

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This investigation includes the study of the effect of added macroions, such as polyethylene glycols of various molecular weights, polyvinyl alcohol and polystyrene sulphonate, NaCl and dioxan on the spectral behaviour and the apparent pK of congo red indicator. It is considered in some cases as a zwitter molecule having the NH_2 and SO_3 sites. The effect on the spectra of pure congo red occurs only in the intensities of the two maxima but no change in their positions was observed.

These changes are explained due to electrostatic types of interaction between the congo red and each of these macroions investigated.

It is commonly recognised that addition of electrolyte in a solution containing a dye in general and a pH -indicator in particular may alter the pK of that indicator. It is known² that addition of electrolyte causes aggregation of the monomer molecules of the dye present in solution or enhances it if it is already taking place. On the other hand, a shift in pK of the free dye occurs whenever polyions and oppositely charged dye molecules coexist in solution^{3,4}. The solution containing cationic dye and an anionic macroion shows positive deviation in pK of the indicator, whereas anionic pH -indicator in presence of cationic macroion shows negative deviation. The observed changes of pK for indicators with opposite charge to that of the polyion is due to specific interactions between dye molecules and monomers of the macroion present in the solution.

Of course, the effect of the molecular weight of the macroion can be of great value as an evidence, for or against the fact that a high charge density on the polyions is the actual cause of the observed ΔpK of the pH -indicator under investigation. Again, changes in the intensity or shifts of the positions of the maxima of the various spectral bands can be due to self-aggregation⁵⁻⁸ of the dye molecules; interaction⁹⁻¹² of the dye molecules with polyions in solution, explained as a function of the aggregation of the dye bound to the polyion; and stacking¹³⁻¹⁷ of dye molecules in the neighbourhood of the chains. In stacking, three very characteristic features may be observed: (i) a large blue-

shift in the absorption band of the dye, (ii) as the concentration of macroions increases, at constant dye concentration, stacking passes through a maxima, because under this condition the dye molecules are distributed between different polyionic domains, and (iii) dioxan, as well as other organic substances inhibit stacking.

Recently we¹⁸ started some systematic and thorough investigation on the pH -indicator-macroion interaction. In the present work the apparent pK of congo red indicator has been determined in solutions of relatively simple charged polyelectrolytes of the weak and strong types. Congo red is of particular interest to us because it is among the first indicators to be discovered and it is categorised as cationic dye. However, from our point of view, it is a zwitter molecule which has NH_2 and SO_3 groups. Therefore, its behaviour in presence of the cationic and anionic macroions should be of interest from the electrostatic point of view.

Experimental

The macroions used were: polyethylene glycols (PEG) (B.D.H.) of various molecular weights, PEG 1000, PEG 400 and PEG 600; polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) (B.D.H.); and poly(sodium styrene sulphonate) (NaPSS), its molecular weight is around 50000. The monomer ethylene glycol (EG), the indicator congo red (CR), dioxan and NaCl (B.D.H.) were used. The solutions were prepared from pure deionised distilled water or in universal

buffers from the commercial solid without further purification.

Two spectrophotometers were used, Pye Unicam SP 8000 when scanning was needed, and Zeiss PMQ-3 when measurements carried out at fixed wavelengths.

Results and Discussion

Congo red has a red color in the alkaline medium and absorbs at 490 nm while it becomes blue in an acidic medium and absorbs at 560 nm. There exists an equilibrium between the two forms of the CR in solution of the type represented by equation (1),

The equilibrium constant of the dissociation can be determined spectrophotometrically using several approaches¹⁹. In our case, the change of optical density with pH was recorded and the pH corresponding to half the total change when going from very acidic (pH < 2.5) to alkaline (pH > 10) solutions was taken as the value of the apparent pK. Whenever necessary, the change in absorption due to dilution was taken into account. The absorption spectra of CR in absence and presence of polyelectrolytes were recorded with a Zeiss QM3 spectrophotometer at 490 and 560 nm bands. pH was varied using the minimum amount of the universal buffer (~ 5 × 10⁻³ M) in order to simplify the experimental determination of the optical densities at pH values near the mid-point of the titration curves of CR. pK value of the CR was first determined in aqueous solution, a very good agreement with literature value²⁰ being obtained. All determinations of apparent pK were made at room temperature (23 ± 1°) and the maximum error was estimated to be ± 0.1 pK units.

The apparent pK of CR in solutions containing macroions, PEG 1000, PEG 4000, PEG 6000, PVA and NaPSS, was determined. Also, determination of its pK in presence of EG, NaCl and dioxan was carried out. In all these solutions a change in the apparent pK, ΔpK, was observed, however, it was not too large as has been noticed in the cases of polyelectrolytes studied by Prini *et al.*⁵. PEG and PVA are weakly cationic polyions, whereas NaPSS is strong anionic polyion. According to the qualitative conclusions reported so far in literature, the pK value for CR shifts towards the higher side, i.e. +ve ΔpK, when present in solutions of -vely charged macroions, and the value also increases with the macroion concentration until a constant value (pK_{max}) is attained. The ΔpK values (Table 1) reveal that it is -ve for EG, PEG 1000 and PEG 6000, but +ve for NaPSS and PEG 4000.

Fig. 1 represents a sample to show the effect of pH on the absorbance of CR in various aqueous solutions containing different macroions.

TABLE 1—pK VALUES OF CR IN VARIOUS SOLUTIONS

Medium (CR, M)	pK	ΔpK
H ₂ O (2.0 × 10 ⁻⁵)	4.50	—
NaPSS (1.0 × 10 ⁻⁴)	4.55	+0.05
(1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵)	4.70	+0.20
(1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶)	4.65	+0.15
EG (1.0 × 10 ⁻³) ¹	3.50	-1.00
(1.0 × 10 ⁻²)	3.63	-0.87
(1.0 × 10 ⁻⁴)	3.60	-0.90
PEG 1000 (1.0 × 10 ⁻³)	3.30	-1.20
(1.0 × 10 ⁻²)	3.32	-1.18
(1.0 × 10 ⁻⁴)	3.30	-1.20
PEG 4000 (1.0 × 10 ⁻³)	4.60	+0.10
(1.0 × 10 ⁻⁴)	4.95	+0.45
H ₂ O (3.0 × 10 ⁻³)	4.60	—
PEG 6000 (1.0 × 10 ⁻⁴)	4.30	-0.30
(5.0 × 10 ⁻⁴)	4.45	-0.15
(1.0 × 10 ⁻³)	3.37	-1.23
H ₂ O (1.5 × 10 ⁻³)	4.25	—
H ₂ O (2.0 × 10 ⁻³)	4.50	—
H ₂ O (3.0 × 10 ⁻³)	4.60	—
Dioxane (0.5)	4.20	-0.30
(1.0)	4.40	-0.10
PVA (4.0 × 10 ⁻³)	4.15	-0.35
(6.0 × 10 ⁻³)	4.35	-0.15
(1.0 × 10 ⁻⁴)	3.85	-0.65
(1.0 × 10 ⁻²)	3.80	-0.70
(1.0 × 10 ⁻³)	3.50	-1.00

Fig. 1. Effect of concentration of PVA on pK values of CR at λ = 490 nm : (●) 2.0 × 10⁻³, (○) 4.0 × 10⁻³, (- -) 6.0 × 10⁻³ and (—) 1.0 × 10⁻² M.

The effect of macroion concentration on the value of pK is not uniform in all the macroions studied, for example, in the case of NaPSS the value decreases as the concentration increases within

the experimental error, which is contrary to that predicted in literature. Whereas for PVA, its $-ve$ value increases as its concentration is increased from 4×10^{-5} to $10^{-3} M$. The same situation is observed for PEG 6000. It is practically constant for PEG 1000 in the concentration range 10^{-4} – $10^{-3} M$. It is worth noting that the addition of NaCl causes a shift in the pK of CR toward the larger side giving $+ve \Delta pK$ values, similar to the effect of added anionic macroions to cationic indicators. However, the addition of dioxane, as an example for organic solvent effect, showed decrease in pK giving $-ve \Delta pK$ values.

One possible explanation of this non-systematic behaviour of CR in these macroion solution is which of the particular site of CR interacting with the corresponding macroion. Though SO_3 is stronger than NH_2 group, the possibility still exists. If the interaction takes place at the NH_2 side, then CR will be acting as anionic rather than cationic dye. On the other hand, if the interaction takes place at the SO_3 side CR will act as cationic dye. Thus our expectation of ΔpK sign¹ is not simple

and straightforward as that in the other simple dyes, like neutral red having only one type of functional group.

We now turn to the effect of added macroions on the spectra of CR at fixed pH conditions. In all our systems under investigators, there is no shift of the positions of the two maxima (490 and 560 nm) of the pure CR in H_2O . However, the intensity of these maxima can remain constant, decrease or increase depending on the added macroion to CR solution. Table 2 shows these changes as a ratio between the optical density of the solution containing the macroion and CR to that of pure H_2O and CR. The effect of concentration of the added macroion in the intensity of the peaks is also recorded in Table 2. The fact that there is no shift in the positions of the two peaks of pure CR, indicates the absence of self-aggregation of the dye molecules. Fig. 2 represents a sample to show the effect of added macroions on the spectral intensity and maximum wavelength(s) of CR at fixed pH values.

TABLE 2—SPECTRAL CHARACTERISTICS OF CONGO RED $2 \times 10^{-5} M$ IN VARIOUS SOLUTIONS

Medium	pH	Concn. M/L	λ_{1max} nm	$\left(\frac{OD}{OD}\right)_{w_1}$	λ_{2max} nm	$\left(\frac{OD}{OD}\right)_{w_2}$
EG	2.73	1.0×10^{-4}	490	1.071	560	1.005
		5.0×10^{-4}	490	1.050	560	1.005
		1.0×10^{-3}	490	1.059	560	1.012
		1.0×10^{-3}	490	1.029	560	1.072
PEG 1000	2.63	1.0×10^{-4}	490	1.117	560	1.062
		1.0×10^{-3}	490	1.100	560	1.178
		1.0×10^{-3}	490	1.079	560	1.134
PEG 4000	2.64	1.0×10^{-4}	490		560	1.032
		5.0×10^{-4}	490		560	1.016
		1.0×10^{-3}	490		560	1.015
		1.0×10^{-3}	490		560	0.918
PEG 6000*	2.65	1.0×10^{-4}	490	1.012	560	0.989
		5.0×10^{-4}	490	1.002	560	1.031
		1.0×10^{-3}	490	0.995	560	1.022
NaPSS	2.86	1.0×10^{-5}	490	1.014	560	1.022
		1.0×10^{-4}	490	1.0036	560	1.038
		1.0×10^{-3}	490	1.0036	560	1.080
PVA	2.86	1.0×10^{-4}	490	0.993	560	0.947
		5.0×10^{-4}	490	1.067	560	1.104
		1.0×10^{-3}	490	1.101	560	1.143
		1.0×10^{-3}	490	1.175	560	1.224
NaCl	2.7	0.1	490	0.990	560	0.850
		0.5	490	0.980	560	0.751
		1.0	490	1.00	560	0.733
Dioxan	2.8	0.1	490	1.022	560	0.993
		0.5	490	1.029	560	0.062
		1.0	490	1.036	560	0.900
	8.35	0.1	490	1.043	560	1.066
		0.5	490	1.131	560	1.274
		1.0	490	1.164	560	1.372
			490		560	

*Congo red, $3 \times 10^{-5} M$.

Fig. 2. Absorbance of CR ($2 \times 10^{-3} M$) in various concentrations of PVA at $pH = 2.86$: (1) 1×10^{-2} , (2) 1×10^{-3} , (3) 5×10^{-4} and (4) $1 \times 10^{-4} M$.

Also the fact that the change in the molecular weight of PEG did not change the pK or the spectral behaviour of the free CR might exclude the possibility of stacking phenomenon. However, the change in pK of CR on addition of macroions suggests some sort of interaction between these macroions with CR. It is our belief that this interaction is electrostatic in nature.

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